

Validation and reliability of the Persian version of the dimensions of *Mastery Questionnaire* (DMQ 18) infant version for assessing mastery motivation in early childhood

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Abstract

Introduction: Mastery motivation is a psychological force that stimulates individuals to concentrate and persistently work towards solving a problem or mastering a relatively challenging skill. This study aimed to determine the validity and reliability of the Persian version of the Dimensions of Mastery Questionnaire (DMQ 18 Infant Version).

Methods: After obtaining a license from the developer of the DMQ-18 test to develop a Persian version, the method recommended by the International Commission Tests was used to ensure semantic, cultural, and conceptual consistency. A retest was administered to 43 parents after two weeks to measure test reliability. Structural validity was assessed through confirmatory factor analysis using AMOS software. Reliability was evaluated using internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) and intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC).

Results: The study included 111 parents (99 mothers and 12 fathers). Confirmatory factor analysis indicated good validity and fit, with seven subscales of mastery motivation showing optimal factor loads (0.48-0.65). Non-significant questions were excluded from the analysis. The total score's Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.92, indicating high reliability. Internal

consistency was acceptable for all subscales (over 0.70), except for mastery pleasure (ICC 0.55, $P=0.007$). Fit indices showed good model fit: χ^2/df , RMSEA, CFI, and NFI were all within acceptable ranges.

Discussion: The Persian version of the DMQ-18 Infant Version is a reliable and valid tool for assessing infant mastery motivation. When used alongside other developmental assessments and clinical observations, it can provide clinicians with a comprehensive understanding of an infant's developmental progress, helping to ensure appropriate interventions are implemented if necessary.

Take-home message: The Persian version of the Dimensions of Mastery Questionnaire (DMQ 18, Infant Version) is reliable and valid for assessing mastery motivation in infants, providing a valuable tool for monitoring and intervening in their development.

Keywords: DMQ 18; children; early childhood assessment behavior; infant development; mastery motivation; psychometrics; Persian version; reliability; validity.

INTRODUCTION

The early years of a child's life are critical, as children rapidly grow cognitively, emotionally, and physically during this period [1]. A key aspect of their development is intrinsic motivation, referred to as mastery motivation in early childhood [2]. Mastery motivation stimulates individuals to persistently work towards solving a problem or mastering a challenging skill [3-5]. This force depends on a child's perseverance and enjoyment while mastering a skill rather than merely completing the task or achieving the desired goal [6,7]. Mastery motivation remains relatively stable in young children and is crucial for academic success, predicting future academic and social achievements even after controlling for IQ and parents' education [8-10].

Mastery motivation drives a child's desire to explore and master their environment, impacting cognitive, social, and emotional development [11]. It aids in developing social relationships, enhancing physical activities, and coping with environmental challenges [12]. Research indicates that early mastery motivation predicts later success in school and adulthood [13,14]. Evidence suggests mastery motivation can forecast future skills in typically developing children and those with developmental disabilities [15,16].

Given mastery motivation's vital role, identifying early childhood deficiencies and developing appropriate interventions are essential. Reliable and valid tools to assess mastery motivation are necessary. The DMQ18 questionnaire is the latest version of this tool. While previous versions of the questionnaire have been translated into Persian, the infant version had not been adapted until now. This study aims to fill that gap by determining the validity and reliability of the Persian version of the DMQ18 Infant Version, thereby providing a valuable tool for assessing mastery motivation in Persian-speaking populations.

METHODS

Study participants

The sample was recruited from families attending well-child medical visit clinics in Tehran, Alborz, and Mazandaran provinces. A total of 111 parents with healthy infants participated. Informed consent was obtained, and participants completed the written questionnaire in the researcher's presence without receiving monetary compensation. Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics of the participants.

Translation and back translation

Two independent translators, fluent in Persian and English, translated the original version into Persian. The translators compared and agreed upon the translations, and a bilingual translator performed the back-translation. The developer approved the final Persian version. Ten parents of children evaluated the questionnaire's formal, content, and cultural validity, preserving 38 main items.

Research procedure

A retest was administered to 43 parents after two weeks to measure the test's reliability. Structural validity was obtained through factor analysis using AMOS software. Reliability was assessed using two-way internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) and intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC). Confirmatory factor analysis was used to assess construct validity, employing various indices to evaluate model fit.

DMQ18 (Infant version)

The questionnaire consists of 38 items on a five-point Likert scale. It is divided into seven sections: Object-Oriented Persistence, Gross Motor Persistence, Social Persistence with Adults, Social Persistence with Children, Mastery Pleasure, Negative Reactions to Challenge-Frustration/Anger, and General Competence.

Ethical aspects

After obtaining a license from the developer of the DMQ18 test, we followed the International Commission Tests' recommended method to ensure the Persian version's semantic, cultural, and conceptual consistency. This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Mazandaran University of Medical Sciences (IR.MAZUMS.REC.1399.126).

RESULTS

Demographic characteristics

Of the 111 parents, 89.2% were mothers, and 11.8% were fathers. The mean age of the infants was 13.1 ± 5.1 months, and 53.2% were boys (Table 1).

Table 1. Child and parents' socio-demographic characteristics (n=111).

Variables	N (%)
Gender	
Boy	59 (53.2)
Girl	52 (46.8)
Relation	
Father	12 (11.8)
Mother	99 (89.2)

Reliability

Table 2 shows ICCs and Cronbach's alpha for the subscales and total score. Cronbach's alpha values ranged from 0.64 to 0.79, indicating acceptable internal consistency for all subscales except for mastery pleasure (ICC 0.55, $P=0.007$). Test-retest reliability was acceptable for most subscales, with ICC values above 0.70, except for mastery pleasure.

Table 2. Cronbach's alpha (N=111) and internal consistency (N=43) of the DMQ18 subscales and total.

DMQ18 Subscales	Cronbach's alpha	ICC (95% CI)	p
Cognitive-Oriented Persistence	0.64	0.75 (0.72-0.89)	0.001

DMQ18 Subscales	Cronbach's alpha	ICC (95% CI)	p
Gross Motor Persistence	0.74	0.78 (0.75-0.88)	0.001
Social Persistence with Adults	0.68	0.71 (0.73-0.87)	0.001
Social Persistence with Children	0.75	0.73 (0.75-0.89)	0.001
Mastery Pleasure	0.75	0.55 (0.56-0.62)	0.007
Negative Reactions	0.74	0.71 (0.75-0.80)	0.001
General Competence	0.79	0.93 (0.86-0.96)	0.001
Total	0.92	0.80 (0.88-0.92)	0.001

Validity

Confirmatory factor analysis showed that all subscales had optimal factor loadings, confirming the questionnaire's construct validity (Table 3).

Table 3. Load factors and significant level DMQ18 (Infant Version) questionnaire.

Subscale	Item	Load Factor
Cognition-oriented Persistence	1	0.31*
	14	0.60*
	17	0.35*
	23	0.63*
	24	0.50*
	29	0.45*
Gross Motor Persistence	3	0.66*
	12	0.82*
	26	0.59*
	36	0.59*
	38	0.42*
Social Persistence with Adults	8	0.47*
	15	0.57*
	19	0.50*
	22	0.36*
	33	0.56*
	37	0.65*
Social Persistence with Children	6	0.62*
	7	0.65*
	25	0.60*
	28	0.46*

Subscale	Item	Load Factor
	32	0.41*
	35	0.70*
Mastery Pleasure	2	0.42*
	11	0.59*
	18	0.76*
	21	0.58*
	30	0.62*
Negative Reactions-frustration/anger	5	0.48
	9	0.74*
	13	0.62*
	16	0.64*
	34	0.54*
General Competence	4	0.43*
	10	0.72*
	20	0.64*
	27	0.79*
	31	0.63*

*P<0.05

The fit indices indicated a good level of model fit (Table 4).

Table 4. Load factor, significant level, and fit indices variable factor structure for DMQ18 (Infant Version).

Subscale	Load Factor	χ^2/df	RMSEA	CFI	NFI	P
Cognition-oriented Persistence	0.48	0.60	0.000	0.92	0.97	0.053
Gross Motor Persistence	0.62	2.98	0.1	0.92	0.89	0.015
Social Persistence with Adults	0.52	1.04	0.02	0.99	0.89	0.042
Social Persistence with Children	0.58	1.76	0.08	0.94	0.88	0.052
Mastery Pleasure	0.60	0.17	0.00	1	0.99	0.051
Negative Reactions-frustration/anger	0.51	1.43	0.06	0.97	0.93	0.022
General Competence	0.65	1.08	0.02	0.99	0.96	0.034

DISCUSSION

The findings show that the Infant Motivation Questionnaire (DMQ18) is a reliable and valid measure for assessing infant motivation. Confirmatory factor analysis demonstrated that all items were significant, indicating a good model fit. The high

participation rate of mothers is consistent with previous research on parenting and child development, but the small number of fathers may limit generalizability.

Several studies have supported the DMQ18's psychometric properties across various populations [4, 21-23, 26-28]. While our study found good reliability and validity for the Infant Motivation Questionnaire, the sample size was relatively small, which may limit the findings' generalizability. Additionally, only parents participated, limiting the range of perspectives.

Despite the low ICC for mastery pleasure, the high alpha for this scale is reassuring, as emotions are not expected to be stable over time. The present study provides valuable insights into the DMQ18's use as a measure of infant motivation. Further studies should investigate the tool's sensitivity, specificity, and generalizability of the findings to a broader population.

Several studies have investigated the psychometric properties of the Dimensions of Mastery Questionnaire (DMQ18) in various populations, including children and adolescents [4, 23-25, 28]

The present study focused specifically on the Infant Motivation Questionnaire, a version of the DMQ designed for use with infants. While the current study found that the Infant Motivation Questionnaire had good reliability and validity, it is essential to note that the sample size was relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the study only included parents as participants, which may limit the range of perspectives represented in the results.

Although the Mastery Pleasure ICC is low, the alpha for this scale is fine. Given that emotions are not expected to be stable over time, the lower ICC is not truly troubling, given this high alpha and the small sample for test-retest.

Despite these limitations, the present study provides valuable insights into using the Infant Motivation Questionnaire to measure infant motivation. The study's findings suggest that the questionnaire is a reliable and valid tool for assessing infant motivation across multiple domains. This is particularly important given motivation's critical role in early childhood development and the potential impact that interventions targeting motivation may have on children's long-term outcomes.

Blasco et al. (2020) found that the DMQ18 had good internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from 0.69 to 0.84 for infants 6-10 months premature and full English term [29]. In addition, another study by Morgan et al. (2017) found similar results for Spanish infants [19].

Saxton et al. (2020) found good internal consistency ($0.81 - 0.84$) in English and Spanish premature infants 18 to 20 months [30].

The DMQ18 had good construct validity, with confirmatory factor analysis supporting the questionnaire's seven-factor structure. Their study is also in line with our research.

Strengths and limitations

This study contributes to the literature by providing evidence of the DMQ18's reliability and validity for infants. However, the sample size was small, and the study did not assess concurrent or criterion validity. Additionally, data on discriminant validity were not collected, and the sensitivity and specificity of the DMQ18 in predicting infant motivation outcomes were not evaluated.

CONCLUSION

The present study provides evidence of the DMQ18's reliability and validity for assessing infant motivation. Further research is needed to confirm these findings in larger and more diverse populations and to evaluate the tool's effectiveness in predicting developmental outcomes. The DMQ-18 infant version, used with other developmental assessments and clinical observations, can provide a comprehensive understanding of an infant's developmental progress.

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References

1. Zuhri MN. Cognitive Psychology Development In The Early Adolescence. *J Educ Soc Issues*. 2023;2(1):44-51.
2. Morgan GA, Józsa K, Liao HF. Introduction to the HERJ special issue on mastery motivation: Measures and results across cultures and ages. *Hung Educ Res J*. 2017;7(2):5-14.
3. Morgan GA, Harmon RJ, Maslin-Cole CA. Mastery motivation: Definition and measurement. *Early Educ Dev*. 1990;1(5):318-339.
4. LaForme Fiss A, Chiarello LA, Hsu LY, McCoy SW. Adaptive behavior and mastery motivation in children with physical disabilities. *Physiother Theory Pract*. 2024 Jul;40(7):1616-1627. doi: 10.1080/09593985.2023.2181118.
5. Maslin-Cole C, Bretherton I, Morgan GA. Toddler mastery motivation and competence: Links with attachment security, maternal scaffolding and family climate. In: Messer DJ (eds), *Mastery Motivation*. Routledge; 1993, pp. 217-241.
6. Choi N, Cho H-J. Temperament and home environment characteristics as predictors of young children's learning motivation. *Early Child Educ J*. 2020;48(5):607-620.
7. Barrett KC, Morgan GA. Mastery motivation: Retrospect, present, and future directions. In: Elliot AJ, *Advances in motivation science*. Elsevier; 2018, pp. 1-39.
8. Lavrijsen J, Vansteenkiste M, Boncquet M, Verschuere K. Does motivation predict changes in academic achievement beyond intelligence and personality? A multitheoretical perspective. *J Educ Psychol*. 2022;114(4):772-790.
9. Liao HF, Wang PJ, Józsa K, Blasco PM, Morgan GA. Understanding and supporting mastery motivation in everyday activities: A focus on early childhood intervention. *J Psychol Educ Res*. 2021;29(2):150-173.
10. Amukune S, Józsa K. Approaches to Learning in Elementary Classrooms: Contribution of Mastery Motivation and Executive Functions on Academic Achievement. *Int J Instr*. 2023;16(2):389-412.
11. Shonkoff JP, Phillips DA. *Neurons to neighborhoods: The science of early childhood development*. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2000.
12. Ryan RM, Deci EL. Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *Am Psychol*. 2000;55(1):68-78.
13. Józsa K, Barrett KC. Affective and social mastery motivation in preschool as predictors of early school success: A longitudinal study. *Early Child Res Q*. 2018;45:81-92.
14. Gilmore L, Cuskelly M. Associations of child and adolescent mastery motivation and self-regulation with adult outcomes: a longitudinal study of individuals with Down syndrome. *Am J Intellect Dev Disabil*. 2017;122(3):235-246.
15. Wang W, Spinrad TL, Eisenberg N. The development and prediction of young children's behavioral mastery motivation. *Early Child Res Q*. 2023;62:239-250.
16. Wang PJ, Morgan GA, Liao HF, Chen LC, Hwang AW, Lu L. Reliability and validity of the revised individualized structured mastery tasks in children with developmental delay. *Int J Phys Med Rehabil*. 2016;4(6):1-7.

17. Wigfield A, Muenks K, Eccles JS. Achievement motivation: What we know and where we are going. *Annu Rev Dev Psychol.* 2021;3: 87-111.
18. Borkowski JG, Thorpe PK. Self-regulation and motivation: A life-span perspective on under achievement. In: Schunk DH, Zimmerman BJ. *Self-regulation of learning and performance.* Routledge; 2023, pp. 45-73.
19. Morgan GA, Liao HF, Szombathelyiné Nyitrai ÁA, Huang SY, Wang PJ, Józsa K. The revised Dimensions of Mastery Questionnaire (DMQ 18) for infants and preschool children with and without risks or delays in Hungary, Taiwan, and the US. *Hung Educ Res J.* 2017;7(2):48-67.
20. Datu JAD, Valdez JPM, Yang W. The academically engaged life of mastery-oriented students: Causal ordering among positive emotions, mastery-approach goals, and academic engagement. *Rev Psicodidáct.* 2022;27(1):1-8.
21. Józsa K, Wang J, Barrett KC, Morgan GA. Age and cultural differences in self-perceptions of mastery motivation and competence in American, Chinese, and Hungarian school age children. *Child Dev Res.* 2014. ID:803061, 16 pages.
22. Özbey S, Dağlıoğlu H. Adaptation study of the motivation scale for the preschool children (DMQ18). *Int J Acad Res.* 2017;4(2):1.
23. Shaoli SS, Islam S, Haque S, Islam A. Validating the Bangla version of the Dimensions of Mastery Questionnaire (DMQ-18) for preschoolers. *Asian J Psychiatr.* 2019;44:143-149.
24. Barrett P. Structural equation modelling: Adjudging model fit. *Pers Individ Dif.* 2007;42(5):815-824.
25. Fagan J, Lee Y. Perceptions and satisfaction with father involvement and adolescent mothers' postpartum depressive symptoms. *J Youth Adolesc.* 2010;39:1109-1121.
26. Barrett KC, Rahmawati A, Józsa K, Liao HF, Morgan GA. Evidence for the validity of the DMQ as a measure of children's mastery motivation. In: Morgan GA, Liao HF, Józsa K (Eds.). *Assessing Mastery Motivation Using the Dimensions of Mastery Questionnaire.* Szent István University Press; 2020.
27. Salavati M, Vameghi R, Hosseini SA, Saeedi A, Gharib M. Mastery motivation in children with cerebral palsy (CP) based on parental report: Validity and reliability of Dimensions of Mastery Questionnaire in Persian. *Mater Sociomed.* 2018;30(2):108-112.
28. Morgan GA, Wang J, Barrett KC, Liao HF, Wang PJ, Huang SY, et al. The Revised Dimensions of Mastery Questionnaire (DMQ 18): A manual and forms for its use and scoring. <http://www.mychhs.colostate.edu/George.Morgan/>. Accessed 10 July 2024.
29. Blasco PM, Acar S, Guy S, Saxton S, Duvall S, Morgan G. Executive function in infants and toddlers born low birth weight and preterm. *J Early Interv.* 2020;42(4):321-337.
30. Blasco P, Saxton S, Gullion LM, Oo TZ, Amukune S, Józsa K. Assessment of Mastery Motivation and Neurodevelopment of Young Children at High Risk for Developmental Delays. *J Intell.* 2023 Jun 9;11(6):115. doi: 10.3390/jintelligence11060115.

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